

**Life cycle of the blood fluke *Sanguinicola armata*
Plehn, 1905 (Digenea: Sanguinicolidae),
parasite of freshwater fishes in Malaysia**

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Abstract

The blood fluke *Sanguinicola armata* is a parasite with a simple, two-host life cycle involving an aquatic mollusc, the intermediate host where cercariae develop, and a fish, which is the definitive host. In Malaysia, *S. armata* was first reported in bighead carp (*Aristichthy nobilis*) and grass carp (*Ctenopharyngodon idella*) fingerlings imported from Taiwan. In 1991, cercariae of *S. armata* have been observed in freshwater snail and the adult fluke in locally produced grass carp fingerlings. Preliminary investigation showed that the snail, *Gyraulus sp.*, was infected with the furcocercous cercariae. Laboratory experiments were carried out to verify the role of this freshwater snail as the intermediate host of the blood fluke. Uninfected snails were exposed to infected grass carp fingerlings for 24 hours and were screened daily for presence of sporocyst or cercariae. For the laboratory infection of uninfected grass carp fingerlings, 102 uninfected grass carp fingerlings were exposed to cercariae for 24 hours. The post-exposed grass carp fingerlings were randomly chosen daily for the examination of *S. armata* infection. Results showed that the sporocyst and cercariae stages of *S. armata* were found in the digestive gland of the snail *Gyraulus convexiusculus*. Cercariae emerged from the infected snails throughout the evening of day-14 up to day-17. These furcocercous cercariae swam actively with alternating periods of passive flotation and infected the definitive host by penetration through the abdominal area. Immature and mature *S. armata* were found in the bulbous arteriosus of *C. idella* on the twelfth and eighteenth day respectively. Immature eggs were seen in gill, liver, kidney and heart on day-18 until day-77. Triangular eggs containing ciliated miracidia were observed only in the gill. Overall, 40 to 43 days were needed for *S. armata* to complete its life cycle at 27°C.

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Introduction

Sanguinicola armata Plehn, 1905, a digenean blood fluke of freshwater cyprinid fish, was first recorded in Malaysia in imported carps, namely bighead carp (*Aristichthys nobilis*) and grass carp (*Ctenopharyngodon idellus*) (Anderson and Shaharom, 1986). Recently, *Sanguinicola armata* has been observed in locally produced grass carp fingerlings (Ong, 1994) but not in any other native fish species (Leong, 1979; Shariff, 1980). Sanguinicolid blood flukes have simple two host life-cycle involving a molluscan intermediate host and a fish definitive host. Kirk and Lewis (1994) have reported on 60 species of blood flukes present in freshwater and marine fishes with 11 known life-cycles. *Sanguinicola inermis* Plehn, 1905 was the first freshwater blood fluke to have its life-cycle described (Odhner, 1911). It was further elucidated by Scheuring (1922) and extensively studied under laboratory conditions by Kirk and Lewis (1993). Smith (1997) reviewed the literature on blood flukes published since 1971, reporting on the life cycles of most *Sanguinicola* species. Ong (1994) redescribed the morphology of the adults of *S. armata* in locally bred grass carp fingerlings. There have been no epizootics caused by *S. armata* in Malaysia or other Asian countries. At present, our knowledge of sanguinicolosis and its impacts on aquaculture is still in an elementary state. Although *S. armata* has been reported from Europe, Russia and Asia (Hu et al., 1965), there are no previous studies on the morphology of its sporocyst and cercariae. From 1991 to 1993, we carried out extensive studies in order to determine the life cycle of this blood fluke.

Materials and Methods

Definitive and intermediate hosts

A total of 100 infected grass carp fingerlings (average size 2-3 cm) obtained from a local supplier in Selangor were used as the source of *S. armata*. Two hundred and fifty uninfected grass carp were supplied by a commercial farm in Melaka. A sample size of 23 infected and 25 uninfected grass carp fingerlings were screened for the infection by *S. armata* based on an assumed prevalence level of infection of 10% of the stock before conducting the transmission experiments. The snail *Gyraulus convexiusculus* were maintained in groups of 20 in 35 L of aerated dechlorinated water in glass aquarium. Eggs were collected daily from the aquarium walls and transferred by pipette to 3 L aquarium tanks. Uninfected juvenile snails from second and third generations were used for transmission experiments two to three weeks post hatching.

Experimental infection of snails

Laboratory infections of snails were conducted in a 13 L aquarium. Thirty uninfected snails were exposed to ten infected grass carp fingerlings for 24 hr. Uninfected snails were placed in Petri dishes, covered with fine mesh net and placed at the bottom of aquaria. The exposed snails were transferred into another 13 L aquarium and screened daily for the presence of sporocysts or cercariae. On day 14, the experimental snails were taken out and kept individually in 15 mL test tubes containing dechlorinated water.

A light was placed on top of each test tube to stimulate cercarial emergence. After 1 - 2 hr, the water from the test tube was poured into a Petri dish and examined using a dissecting microscope. The cercariae were counted and used for laboratory infection of uninfected grass carp fingerlings. Living specimens were also stained with vital stain (0.01% neutral red) and observed using a compound microscope equipped with Nomarski and phase-contrast optics. The specimens were drawn using a camera lucida, followed by measurement and photography. All measurements are given in micrometers (μm).

Experimental infection of grass carp fingerlings

Laboratory transmission experiments were carried out in 40 L aquaria. One hundred two uninfected grass carp fingerlings were exposed to 300 cercariae for 24 hr. The cercariae were introduced into the infection arena in approximately 15 L of water, and after exposure, the fingerlings were transferred into a 100 L aquarium and maintained at 27°C. Exposed fishes were randomly selected and killed for daily observation. The experiment was terminated when adults or eggs were found.

Results

The snail *Gyraulus convexiusculus* was found to be infected by *S. armata* on day one (24 hr after exposure), the sporocysts and cercariae being found in the host's digestive gland. Young mother sporocysts developed on day one and contained several cells (Plate 1A). Larger sporocysts were seen on day 10 and day 11 (Plate 1B). Young mother sporocysts were round and became elongated as they developed into mature sporocysts. In shape, sporocysts were variably thin-walled, nonmotile and unbranched. Daughter sporocysts containing immature cercariae which developed individually inside the thin sporocyst membrane were seen on day 12 (Plate 1C and 1D). A maximum of two to three immature cercariae were found inside each sporocyst. Fully formed cercariae were observed on days 14, 15, 16 and 17. It took 14 to 15 days for snails to become infected. The prevalence of miracidia of *S. armata* in infected snails is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Percentage of snails infected with *Sanguinicola armata* in laboratory experiments

Experiment	Number of infected fish	Number of snails			Dead	Percentage infection
		Exposed	Examined	Infected		
1	10	30	26	11	4	42.3
2	10	30	26	10	4	38.5
3	10	30	23	9	7	39.1
Total	30	90	75	30	15	41.0
Control	10	30	30	0	0	0.0

The cercariae infected the fish host by penetrating through the abdominal wall as observed using a dissecting microscope. The cercariae were furcocercous, with a kidney-shaped body ($n=20$, 67.2–9.7 mm long and 28.2–8.2 mm wide) and a long tubular tail ($n=20$, 201.6–12.2 mm) with a forked end (Plate 1E). The anterior organ was telescopic, encircled by several rows of barbed spines and delineated from the body. The longitudinal and circular muscles were well developed. The forked tail was surrounded by a thin laterally compressed membrane. There were 10 to 11 pairs of sensory hairs distributed along its length. The life span of cercariae was about five hr at 26°C and up to seven hr at 22°C. Examination of 102 grass carp fingerlings which had been exposed to *S. armata* cercariae showed that 74.5% were infected and 3.9% of the fish were dead. Sixteen immature blood flukes measuring 206.0–47.6 mm long and 59.2–18.0 mm wide were found on day 12 from four grass carp fingerlings. The worms were considered immature as they did not have any development of the reproductive organs. On day 18, a butterfly-shaped ovary with ten pairs of testes were seen in three adult flukes from six grass carp fingerlings. The three mature flukes measured 341.1–45.7 mm long and 54.9–8.3 mm wide (Plate 2A). A total of 18 days were needed for the cercariae to develop into adult fluke in the definitive host. Numerous non-operculated eggs were observed in gill smears from grass carp fingerlings taken between day 18 until day 77. Eggs were also found encapsulated in the heart, kidney and liver. Newly laid eggs of size 40.3–3.6 mm in length and 21.5–3.0 mm in width ($n=30$) contained several vitelline cells; only one zygote cell was observed (Plate 2B & 2C). However, vitelline cells were not seen when the four tiers of cilia appeared on the miracidia, which contained fully formed rodlet cells, a bilobed eyespot and a pair of penetration glands with one long stylet in the mid portion of the anterior end (Plate 4D). The width and length of the miracidium of *S. armata*, from 30 snails averaged 481.0–0.6 mm and 7.1–1.2 mm ($n=30$), respectively. Immature eggs started to form active miracidia within 6 days.

Discussion

The morphology of the adult flukes, eggs, miracidia, sporocysts and cercariae observed in the present study were characteristic of *S. armata*. The lanceolate-shaped adult fluke with marginal spines on both sides of the body, a butterfly-shaped ovary and ten pairs of testes corresponded to the description for adult *S. armata* provided by Ong (1994). The triangular eggs and the miracidial stages correspond well with the description by Anderson and Shaharom-Harrison (1986). As both mother and daughter sporocysts were found in infected snails, two sporocyst generations occur in the life-cycle of *S. armata*. Kirk and Lewis (1993) mentioned that two sporocyst generations took place in the life-cycle of *S. inermis*; however, most publications on freshwater sanguinicolids report only the daughter sporocyst generation. Tang and Ling (1975) reported that only the daughter sporocyst was found in *S. lungensis*. Meade and Pratt (1965) mentioned that a mother sporocyst was not found in *S. alseae*. However, Herbert (1992) highlighted that one or more sporocyst generations may occur in sanguinicolid blood flukes. As, more cercariae can be produced if more sporocyst generations occur, this increases the possibilities for the

Plate 1: (A): Sporocyst of *Sanguinicola armata* on day one with germ cells inside the membrane (M). (B): Mature mother sporocyst on day 11 with several cells containing the germ cells within the membrane (M). (C): Immature cercaria (IM) with the forked part of tail (FT) clearly differentiated in the membrane. (D): Cercaria increasing in size within the membrane. (E): A mature cercaria with the body (B) consisting of dorsal fin (DF), sensory hair (SH) on the tail (T) and forked part of the tail (FT). Scale bar given in Figure E applies to all figures: A & B (26 mm), C-D (20 mm) and E (26 mm)

Plate 2: Adult and eggs in various stages of development of *Sanguinicola armata*. Note: (A): Adult found on day 18. (B): Newly laid egg. (C): Immature egg contained three vitelline cells (VC). (D): Mature egg containing miracidia (MI) with eyespot (E), germ cell (GC) and a pair of sacs (SA) in the egg shell. Scale bar in Figure D applies to all figures: A (49 mm.) B (8 mm), C (20 mm) and D (4 mm).

cercariae to attack the final host. No birth pore or pharynx was observed on the sporocyst surface using a light microscope. This suggests that no redial stages are formed in this species. The furcocercous cercaria of *S. armata*, with a kidney-shaped body and a long tubular tail with a forked end fits the general description for sanguinicolid cercariae as given by Kirk and Lewis (1993).

In the present study, *S. armata* completed their life cycle in 40 to 43 days at 27°C, which was much shorter as compared with the life cycle of *S. inermis*, which took 90 days and *S. idahoensis*, which required 56 days (Schell, 1974). It only took 14 to 15 days for miracidia of *S. armata* to form cercarial stages in the intermediate host (Fig. 1). Kirk and Lewis (1993) highlighted that cercariae of *S. inermis* emerged from the snail *Lymnaea peregra* at 30 - 38 days post-exposure to miracidia. In another study by Schell (1974), cercariae of *S. idahoensis* were observed in *Lithoglyphus virens* after 58 - 70 days exposure to miracida. The pattern of cercarial emergence from the snail and penetration of the fish could also be influenced by environmental factors such as temperature and water quality including chemicals in the water and condition of the host tissue. Iqbal and Sommerville (1986) reported that the peak production of cercariae of *S. inermis* occurred in summer, as higher temperature increased metabolism and accelerated the development of larval stages in the snail tissue. In tropical countries, the water temperature is high (25°C - 30°C) and does not fluctuate markedly throughout the year. Hence, the development of miracida to sporocyst and cercariae could be accelerated. The developmental pattern may differ markedly in different hosts and environments, host populations or even in different strains of the same host (Smyth and Hutton, 1983). The prevalence of infection in snails, ranging from 38.5% - 42.3%, was relatively low in this study. This could be due to the low number of miracidia entering the host or to variability within the snails. Shostak and Esch (1990) commented that in most cases, responses may change with variations in environmental conditions. Sporocysts and cercariae of *S. armata* were abundant in the digestive glands of the infected snails. According to Ginetsinskaya (1988), metamorphosis takes 2 to 3 days to complete in the snail tissue and in some cases, the mother sporocyst will only form when it reaches a definitive location, which is mostly reported as the digestive glands. The same locations in snail intermediate hosts for sanguinicolid species were also mentioned by Kirk and Lewis (1993). The most probable reason is the availability of high nutrients in the digestive gland (Haas, 1992). Ginetsinskaya (1988) reported that most immature stages of trematodes are observed in high nutrient areas, such as the digestive glands.

The low mortality (3.9%) in grass carp fingerlings in the present study could be due to the size and condition of the fish. An abundance of eggs and miracidia released by mature worms were observed in the gills. Extensive damage to fish gills due to sanguinicolid infection was reported by several authors (Wales, 1958; Hoffman, 1967; Kirk and Lewis, 1992). However, the presence of one or two eggs in the gill capillaries will not kill the fish (Davis et al., 1961). This could account for the low mortality in infected grass carp fingerlings seen in this study. Iqbal and Sommerville (1986) reported

Fig. 1. The life cycle of *Sanguinicola armata*.

a mortality of 31% in common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) during a 12-month study of experimental infection by *S. inermis*. They found that the critical stage was during the period of egg production by the adult fluke. A similar phenomenon was also seen in the case of *S. armata*. It is believed that more adult worms evidently deposit larger numbers of eggs, which can cause obstruction of the blood vessels in the fish. Small-size fish could be more susceptible to cercarial attack, as softer tissues provide easier penetration. The number of cercariae to which the fish is exposed also influences survival. Kirk and Lewis (1993) reported that exposure to 2500 cercariae of *S. inermis* would kill carp within 1 - 5 hr after invasion. However, when exposed to lower doses of cercariae, the fish survived for up to 30 days. In the present study, the number of cercariae which entered individual grass carp fingerlings was not known. In addition, it is obvious that the eggs of this fluke are pathogenic to fish due to the host reaction they cause, especially in the heavily infected individuals. More studies on this aspect are needed, as *S. armata* may be a real threat to the fish farming industry.

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